

Denoising of MRI Images Using Sub Band Adaptive Thresholding Technique with Neighbourhood Pixel Filtering Algorithm

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Abstract--- Image denoising has become popular in medical imaging especially in the Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI). Initially we Presented Subband adaptive thresholding technique based on wavelet coefficient for reducing the noise in MRI Images, latter this technique is used along with Neighbourhood Pixel Filtering Algorithm (NPFA)for denoising MRI Images. Using Maximum Likelihood (ML) estimator or a Maximum a Posterior (MAP) estimator, a statistical model is proposed to calculate the noise variance for each coefficient based on the subband. A new mechanism for reduction of noise by joining the wavelet denoising technique with optimized thresholding function is also presented with this model. The quality of being clear is improved in image by finding Neighbourhood Pixel Difference (NPD) and combining NPFA along with subband thresholding. With least square method, by minimizing NPD and Weighted Mean Square Error (WMSE), the filtered value is generated. A minimization of noise in noise pixel is obtained to the best using NPFA filter solution. The consequence of an action of both high pass and low pass filter can be obtained with this NPFA Filter. Hence the proposed technique results significantly superior image quality by preserving the edges, with better PSNR value. Further, the proposed Subband thresholding technique along with NPFA filter technique is compared with other filters like Median filter and Weiner Filter.

Keywords--- Subband Thresholding, Magnetic Resonance Image (MRI), Wavelet Decomposition, Neighbourhood Pixel Filter Algorithm (NPFA), Optimum Thresholding.

I. Introduction

In this depending on the sub band using Maximum Likelihood (ML) estimator, noise variance is calculated for each Wavelet coefficient. To create the threshold value dependent on decomposition level, multiplying factor (α) is used in the optimum threshold formula. Now apply NPFA filter to each coefficient to get better quality of image from corrupted image. This NPFA filter looks at the neighbouring pixel values and cease high frequency signal from whole noisy signals. This filter conducts like a LPF in smooth region by reducing noise variance adequately and providing identical weights to all its neighboring pixels. Apply soft thresholding to every noisy coefficient after finding threshold and then the multi-scale decomposition inverting is done to reconstruct the better quality of images with less blurring.

II. Wavelet Coefficient Model

Wavelet coefficients having large weight indicate the edges or some textures, where as those with small weights are related with smooth regions represent the background. In these regions variance for each sub band are determined by ML estimator. This method gives successful results but not meet the requirements at object edges where there are no smooth variations in the variance field. To beat this, the each subband coefficients are partitioned into two classes known as significant class and insignificant class except the first fine scale. The high activity regions represents significant class and smooth regions indicates insignificant class. The sizes of these two classes are under the control of significance threshold T.

If the weight is greater than T then the coefficient is placed in significant class else it is to be placed in insignificant class. The histogram of the coefficient in insignificant class concentrated more near zero where as more spread out in histogram in significant class. Hence the significant class coefficients are modelled as statistically independent identically distributed Laplacian with zero mean. The insignificant class coefficients are corresponds to homogeneous regions.

2.1. Statistical Model

The examined model is denoted as follows $Y = X + V$, where the wavelet transform of the degraded image is Y , wavelet transform of the original image is X , V denotes the wavelet transform of the noise components having Gaussian distribution $N(0, \sigma_V^2)$. Since X and V are mutually independent, the variances of Y , X and V are given by

$$\sigma_Y^2 = \sigma_X^2 + \sigma_V^2 \quad (1)$$

III. Noise Variance Estimation

The following step wise procedure is used for each wavelet coefficients depending on the subband to calculate the variance estimate.

Step 1: From the first decomposition level diagonal subband HH_1 , the noise variance σ_V^2 can be estimated from accurate median estimator.

$$\sigma_V^2 = \left[\frac{\text{median } |y(V)|}{0.6745} \right]^2 \quad (2)$$

Where $y(V)$ indicates the coefficients HH_1 subband.

Step 2: The coarse subband has very high SNR hence they are not processed.

Step 3: Within the subband, Horizontal, vertical and diagonal oriented three sub bands coefficients are modelled as identically independently distributed with zero mean and variance $\sigma_{x,j}^2$ (where j indicates the subband). The variance estimate is determined from the noisy coefficients in subband j as

$$\sigma_{x,j}^2 = \max\{0, \text{Var}\{\bar{y}_i, i \in \text{subband } j\} - \sigma_V^2\} \quad (3)$$

Using MAP, $\bar{x}$ is obtained by a soft threshold λ as given in equation (4) to each noisy coefficient.

$$\lambda = \sqrt{2\sigma_V^2 / \sigma_{x,j}^2}, j \in \text{subband} \quad (4)$$

Step 4: Coefficients are assigned either to significant or insignificant classes based on the magnitude of the estimated coefficients by comparing with significance threshold T in each of high sub bands, where

$$T = \sigma \sqrt{2 \log N^2} \quad (5)$$

1. Significant class Coefficients are modelled as zero mean identically independently distributed Laplacian and their variance $\sigma_{x,insig}^2$ is determined from the noisy coefficients as mentioned in step 3. Next the MAP estimator is used.
2. Insignificant class coefficients having small magnitude representing smooth areas, $\sigma_{x,insig}^2$ is estimated using ML estimator for a local neighborhood.

Where variance is assumed to be constant. The estimate of the class coefficient variance is

$$\sigma_{x,insig}^2 = \frac{1}{M} (\sum_{V=1}^M y^2(V) - \sigma_V^2) \quad (6)$$

Where M represents the number of wavelet coefficients present in local neighborhood N . For insignificant class the MAP estimator is given by

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sigma_{x,insig}^2}{\sigma_{x,insig}^2 + \sigma_V^2} \bar{y}_i \quad (7)$$

IV. Neighborhood Pixel Filtering Algorithm (NPFA)

The algorithm initially identifies whether the input B_{ij} noisy pixel value is corrupted itself by a noise or not. The noise reduction is done by using frame models as shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. By comparing the pixel value of the current pixel B_{ij} to that of the neighboring pixels $B_{i-1,j}$, $B_{i+1,j}$, $B_{i,j-1}$, $B_{i,j+1}$ and place pixel P_{ij} in the previous wavelet frame. Identify the Neighbouring Pixel Difference (NPD) by calculating difference between the neighbouring pixel values say $B_{i-1,j}$, $B_{i+1,j}$, $B_{i,j-1}$, $B_{i,j+1}$ and current pixel P_{ij} from the pixel value B_{ij} . If all the differences are greater than a

specified threshold T then the pixel B_{ij} is said to be corrupted by a noise. Otherwise it is not. After detection of noise pixel, a filtered value f_{ij} would be assigned for each detected noisy pixel as the weighted average of its neighbouring pixel values in the NPFA frame given by Eq. (8).

$$f_{ij} = \frac{B_{i-1,j} + B_{i+1,j} + B_{i,j+1} + B_{i,j-1}}{4} \quad (8)$$

Fig.1: Wavelet Frame

Fig. 2: Neighbourhood Pixel Filter Frame

The difference between the noisy pixel value B_{ij} and its original pixel value would be reflected by NPD. For corrupted pixels this correlation is small between the pixel differences and a value f_{ij} is allocated to each current pixel in order to estimate the original pixel value of current pixel. The pixel value with noise is highly correlated than the original pixel value. In this situation by minimizing NPD, the filtered value f_{ij} will be generated and Weighted Mean Square Error (WMSE) which is given in Eq. (12) using method of Least Squares. For which the weight W_{ij} of each pixel is required which depends on NPD and calculated using Eq. (9) and Eq. (10)

$$W_{ij} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^N g(i) [P_{ij} - B_{ij}] * f_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^N g(i) [P_{ij} - B_{ij}]} \quad (9)$$

$$g(i) = \begin{cases} 2^{(\lfloor T/8 \rfloor - \lfloor i/8 \rfloor)} & i < T \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Where P_{ij} is the current pixel value, B_{ij} is the noisy pixel value, f_{ij} is the filtered value.

A reduction in noise pixel is identified by replacing NPFA filter solution obtained from Eq. (13) with the noisy value of current pixel. This NPFA filter reduces noise variance in smooth regions utmost by assigning same weights to all neighbouring pixels, acts as LPF which preserves edge information. In high texture region, NPFA filter attenuates high pass features by giving small weight for that pixel at the discontinuities and maintains the sharpness of edges, cuts off high frequency signal only among all noisy signals. Quantitative measure of PSNR value calculation from Eq. (11) with the use of minimized WMSE. Hence NPFA filter gives better PSNR values to than other wavelet method.

$$PSNR = 10 \log_{10} \left[\frac{255^2}{WMSE} \right] dB \quad (11)$$

Minimize

$$WMSE = \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^N W_{ij} (B_{ij} - Y_{ij})^2 \quad (12)$$

Y_{ij} is the NP Filter Algorithm for denosing solution given by the following equation:

$$Y_{ij} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^N W_{ij} B_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^N W_{ij}} \quad (13)$$

V. Selection of Threshold and Proposed Technique

The choice of threshold determines the efficacy of denoising technique because wavelet transform reduces the noise by removing insignificant coefficients based on threshold.

5.1. Selection of Threshold

A small threshold value gives an output which is close to the input, but still there may be noise in result. A large threshold value generates a image with greater number of zero coefficients causes smoothing in signal or image, smoothing causes blurring, so optimum thresholding value is required. For different DWT decomposition Levels, Soft thresholding method is used to analyze the performance of denoising system. Also it leads to less severe distortion of the object of interest than other thresholding methods. To implement a soft threshold of the DWT coefficients for a particular wavelet band, the coefficients of that band should be threshold by Compute the sample variance σ^2 of the coefficients in each band and set the threshold to any multiple of standard deviation σ for that band as shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4. The soft thresholding is generally represented by,

$$d_{ik}^{soft} = \begin{cases} sign(d_{ik})(|d_{ik}| - \lambda^*) & \text{if } |d_{ik}| > \lambda^* \\ 0 & \text{if } |d_{ik}| \leq \lambda^* \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Fig. 3: Soft threshold Characteristics

Fig. 4: Soft threshold Characteristics with $\lambda = 1$ with $\lambda = \alpha\sigma$

5.2. Optimum Value Threshold

Depending on the decomposition level, optimum thresholding is fixed. At every decomposition level, four frequency sub bands LL, LH, HL, and HH are obtained. To the low frequency subband LL the next decomposition level should be applied. This process is repeated until specified level (level 2) is reached. To overcome smoothing problem and to get better quality of image, the multiplying factor α is used in the threshold formula to get better PSNR value by keeping better edges where

$$\alpha = 2^{L-K} \sqrt{\log M} \quad (15)$$

L is the no. of wavelet decomposition level, K is the level where the subband is available, M is the total number of wavelet coefficients. With this multiplication factor α the optimum threshold formula for the proposed scheme is given by

$$\lambda^* = \alpha \lambda \quad (16)$$

Where λ , σ are calculated using Eq. (4) and Eq.(15) respectively.

5.3. Proposed Technique

Denoising of MRI image can be done in two stages. Denoising is performed by using Subband adaptive thresholding technique without adding NPFA filter in first stage.

The PSNR values measured are given in Table 1 and Fig. 7 shows qualitative measure based on the following steps.

Fig. 5: Image Denoising using Adaptive Subband Thresholding Technique without NPFA Filter (Stage-1 of Proposed Technique)

The Steps involved in the proposed wavelet based denoising technique without NPFA filter (Stage-1) are given here:

Input & Output: Noisy image, Denoised image respectively.

Step 1: By using Wavelet Transform perform multiscale decomposition of the image corrupted by Gaussian noise.

Step 2: Using Eq. (1) calculate Noise Variance σ_v^2 for each scale and determine the scale parameter.

Step 3: From the noisy coefficient in subband j using Eq. (2) variance estimate is determined for each of the three sub bands..

Step 4: Using Eq. (2) and Eq. (3) determine of the class coefficient variance in each of the other high sub bands.

Step 5: Using optimum value threshold formula as given in Eq. (16), find out threshold value after calculation of the multiplying factor α for each subband using Eq.(15). After computing threshold for each subband except the low pass or approximation subband, apply soft thresholding using threshold given in Eq. (14) to each wavelet coefficient, by substituting the threshold value obtained in Step 5.

Step6: Multiple decomposition inversion is performed to reconstruct the denoised image which is original image.

Before applying soft thresholding to the Subband NPFA filter is added in second stage. To each wavelet coefficients in the entire subband except the LL_1 this NPFA Filter is added, reduction of noise in subband is observed by replacing the optimal weight that is NPFA filter solution with the noisy values of the current pixel. The PSNR values measured are given in Table 2 and Fig. 7 shows qualitative measure based on the following steps.

Fig. 6: Image Denoising Using Adaptive Subband Thresholding Technique Along with NPFA Filter (Stage-2 of Proposed Technique)

The Steps involved in the proposed wavelet based denoising technique with NPFA filter (Stage-2) are given here:

Input & Output: Noisy image, Denoised image respectively.

Step 1: By using Wavelet Transform perform multiscale decomposition of the image corrupted by Gaussian noise.

Step 2: Using Eq. (1) calculate Noise Variance σ_v^2 for each scale and determine the scale parameter.

Step 3: From the noisy coefficient in subband j using Eq. (2) variance estimate is determined for each of the three sub bands.

Step 4: Using Eq. (2) and Eq. (3) determine of the class coefficient variance in each of the other high sub bands.

Step 5: To each coefficient in all the three sub bands add NPFA Filter except the low pass subband.

Step 6: Using the Eq. (13) for each coefficient determine optimal NPFA filter solution.

Step 7: Using optimum value threshold formula as given in Eq. (16), find out threshold value after calculation of the multiplying factor α for each subband using Eq.(15).

Step 8: After computing threshold for each subband except the low pass or approximation subband, apply soft thresholding using threshold given in Eq. (14) to each wavelet coefficient, by substituting the threshold value obtained in Step 7.

Step 9: Multiple decomposition inversion is performed to reconstruct the denoised image which is original image.

VI. Experimental Results

The implemented algorithm was tested with Weiner Filtering, Median Filtering, subband Adaptive Threshold Technique with and without NPFA filtering in wavelet domain in MAT Lab environment. To estimate the filter performance PSNR of the MRI images have been calculated by using the Eq.(17) and Eq. (18) for the first and second stages of algorithm.

Stage 1

$$PSNR = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{255^2}{MSE} \right) dB \quad (17)$$

Where

$$MSE = \frac{1}{MN} \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^N (X_{ij} - Y_{ij})^2$$

Table1: PSNR Values Using Subband Wavelet Method with Different Noise Level

Noise Image	Noisy Variance	Subband Wavelet Method
45.04	0.055	50.27
45.89	0.05	51.26
46.85	0.045	52.43
47.92	0.04	53.75
49.15	0.035	55.27
50.56	0.03	57.03
52.25	0.025	59.11
54.33	0.02	61.67
57.05	0.015	64.88
60.91	0.01	66.78

Stage 2

$$PSNR = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{255^2}{WMSE} \right) dB \quad (18)$$

Where

$$WMSE = \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^N W_{ij} (B_{ij} - Y_{ij})^2$$

Table 2: PSNR Value Using Subband Wavelet Method Using NPFA Filter with Different Noise Level

Noise Image	Noisy Variance	Subband Wavelet Method	NPFA filtering
45.04	0.055	50.27	57.04
45.89	0.05	51.26	57.72
46.85	0.045	52.43	58.44
47.92	0.04	53.75	59.24
49.15	0.035	55.27	60.09
50.56	0.03	57.03	61.04
52.25	0.025	59.11	62.14
54.33	0.02	61.67	63.37
57.05	0.015	64.88	64.95
60.91	0.01	66.78	69.39

Fig. 7: Denoising of Magnetic Resonance Image (MRI) Corrupted by Gaussian Noise $\sigma^2= 0.01$

Also graphical representation based on the performance of various filter with the corresponding PSNR value is given in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8: Graphical Representation of Performance of Various Filters with the Corresponding PSNR Value for MRI Image

VII. Conclusion

The proposed technique gives us the best quality of image edge preserving and good PSNR value. This NPFA filter gains the effect of both high pass and low pass filter as the low pass filter preserving the energy of signal and attenuating the high pass features at the discontinuities. This filter uses NPD concept, instead of all noisy signals cuts off high frequency only. After implementing NPFA filter, it is observed that there is a significant improvement in clarity and sharpness of the image. Studies have been made in this paper between Median filter Wiener filter, subband thresholding technique with and without NPFA. The outcome of the study reveals that the NPFA filter with subband thresholding performs well than the other filters in terms of PSNR and visual quality.

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